

HYGIENE CULTURE IN STUDENTS DEVELOPING HEALTH CARE THINKING PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF FORMATION

Kholmatova Muzayyan

Independent student of Kokan State Pedagogical Institute
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8171126>

Abstract: the article describes the factors of developing the professional and personal qualities of a teacher at a sufficient level to conduct the educational process of forming the mindset of health care in the development of hygienic culture in students as a pedagogical competence. Pedagogical competence is directly related to educational efficiency, and it is emphasized that a teacher with pedagogical competence is a person who provides high level of educational efficiency. From this point of view, the pedagogical competence in the activity of the teacher becomes a complex reality consisting of several important directions.

Key words: intellectual aspect, management aspect, psychological aspect, pedagogical aspect, communicative aspect, reflexive aspect.

Today, it is evident that one of the urgent tasks is to form the mindset of health care in society, treat health as a value, develop the criteria for cultivating a healthy lifestyle culture, and expand the scope of conducting scientific research in this regard. In his address to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev specifically emphasized that "it is necessary to promote a healthy lifestyle among the population"[1]. The reason for this is that reforms are carried out with healthy people, the value of a person is determined by his health, a healthy lifestyle, the establishment of hygienic procedures, as well as the tasks of raising a healthy generation. Therefore, in the development of hygienic culture in students, it is necessary to form the mindset of protecting, appreciating and rationally treating health.

Health pedagogy ("health care") focused on the preservation of human health is rapidly developing at the heart of innovative changes in the education and training system in the world. "Physical and mental health and well-being of the population determines the level of civilization of the state and shows the indicator of sustainable development of the nation. In this place, the formation of thinking and need for health protection in a person becomes important, and the scope of research that serves to ensure pedagogical efficiency in health infrastructures in the society is observed. In the world education system, the health of the growing generation is honored as a national value of any nation, and this issue is approached as an important socio-pedagogical task, and the need to carry out scientific research on the issues that determine the state's perspective, the nation's gene pool, the economic, intellectual, anthropogenic potential of the country's development, its demographic support, and the issues that determine the development of the society is manifested. This is the application of constructive-prophylactic technologies aimed at the health of young people, systematic and integrated models in the educational process, the use of invariant-differentiated technologies designed to protect students from the effects of harmful habits" [2], a new approach to the content of the rational organization of valeological and preventive

activities of educational institutions, social institutions, families and individuals, issues of vision, attitude, essence, form, criterion, improvement of demand have gained particular relevance. showing his work.

Recently, the process of understanding such concepts as health, health care and protection, healthy lifestyle, healthy thinking as a historical-social, philosophical-psychological, moral-aesthetic category has been observed. Because the health care process is a broad concept, its components and requirements are very broad and multifaceted. In the existing researches in Uzbekistan, there are a number of approaches that try to clarify the social, medical and pedagogical essence of "health", "lifestyle", "healthy lifestyle", "healthy culture", "hygienic education", "health values", "health protection", "health principles", "health care", "healthy thinking". So, if the students' health care mentality is formed, it will be possible to create an environment of health care in the whole society. According to O. Jamoldinova, "the concept of culture is based on thinking. It is the factor that distinguishes a civilized person from an uncivilized person that manifests itself in the process of certain "knowledge, skills and abilities" formed in a person. Because the value of health, according to I.Yu. Abrosimova, is a mindset built on the basis of the great importance of health for a person, its importance does not lose its importance for the human society, every individual, social groups, and classes, and it is considered the main humanitarian value that is transmitted from generation to generation for all of them" [3].

The meaning of the word "Health" corresponds to the concepts of health, health, and health. The meaning of the word "Care" corresponds to the words to protect, to show kindness, to preserve. Having "health care" is a scientific-theoretical view, idea, knowledge, character, behavior and moral norms, lifestyle, action, effort, and activity about maintaining health in the way of living, and it is the implementation and manifestation of economic, social, educational and labor relations with the environment in a person's way of life in a mutually coordinated, non-damaging and protected manner.

In the USA, seven main areas of systematization of health care, i.e., areas of responsibility and priority, have been defined, these areas have been implemented and are widely active. These areas are called seven responsible areas of health care pedagogy.

Among the seven important areas of health pedagogy are: (1) strategy, activities and programs of implementation of health protection pedagogy; (2) management of health education strategies, activities, and programs; (3) research on health and health care issues; (4) development and financial support of research on health pedagogy; (5) planning health pedagogy strategies, activities and programs; (6) organization of services aimed at personal health; (7) areas such as the study of needs for personal and public health protection are introduced.

If we compare some places in the traditional content and directions of health care thinking in foreign countries with existing concepts in our country, the following results show their similarities and differences.

"Health care" thinking is a product of the social environment. It is a historical-social, philosophical-psychological, moral-aesthetic and pedagogical category. As a pedagogical category, it is not formed outside of the social environment. Pedagogical environment is necessary for its formation. Therefore, in order to form the mindset of "health care", it is necessary to create a social environment capable of forming it.

We defined the social content of "health care" thinking in the formation of students' hygienic culture as follows:

Personal health care requirements of students: ensuring physical health, obeying medical norms regarding body movements, regular medical examinations, knowing the medical indicators of one's body and understanding their content, for example, ultrasound, general and biochemical diagnosis of blood, regular physical training, knowing the basics of reproductive health, protecting oneself from sexual diseases and relationships, boyhood and girlhood, protecting virginity, family knowing the basics of health, knowing the harm of technical tools, especially IT technologies, etc.

Features of "health care" that arise in connection with the social environment in which students live: "changing socio-political reality, scientific development, in particular, genetics, innovative pharmaceuticals, "intelligent-smart" drugs, cloning, artificial growth of body parts, implantation of body parts, body technologies, creation of artificial body parts, globalization, modern environmental, financial, ideological threats, rapid development of trade, mixing of cultures, artificial goods, including food, such as artificial rice, eggs, harmful toys, the spread of infectious and difficult-to-control diseases"[4], protection from ideological insanity, etc.

Ownership of the "health care" mindset is a spiritual, moral, ideological quality, a set of personal ideas, views, and positions aimed at health protection, which a person manifests in his life as a stable and stable life goal and way of life.

In the pedagogical process in the direction of health care, the teacher is required to fulfill the following requirements in relation to the content of education: scientificity; educational and developmental character of the process; inextricably linked with lifestyle, modern demands and innovations, working with information technologies and various gadgets; ensuring the integral connection between theory and practice; innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process; use of interactive methods, in particular, pedagogical technologies of health care.

The idea of raising a mentally and physically healthy generation has a historical character, and it has been formed as a vital need with the emergence of humanity and has been improving in content. In particular, religious views that arose as a social need (animism, fetishism, totemism, Buddhism), the holy book of Zoroastrians, Avesta, the important sources of Islamic culture, the Holy Qur'an, Hadith Sharif, examples of folk oral creativity, it is emphasized that living a healthy life is a guarantee of having a healthy mindset, an important factor for the health of society, and people are called to lead a healthy lifestyle.

In the development of a healthy generation, the foundation of physical maturity should be built on the basis of spiritual maturity. Spiritual culture is an important index that determines the formation of "health care" in young people. Genres of folk pedagogy in the education of a spiritually cultured person: epics, fairy tales, narrative proverbs, riddles, quick sayings, songs, ritual folklore, children's folklore, caress and tricks are important tools.

The success of the process of ensuring integrity and continuity in the development of "health care" for young people is guaranteed by the decision of the technological approach to this process. In the development of "health care" in young people, creating a mechanism for organizing the educational process and implementing it, determining the specific characteristics, opportunities, conditions of educational subjects, indices and indicators that determine the level of formation of "health care", and focusing educational goals and tasks on the basis of the development of a model of a person with "health care" is a guarantee of positive results.

Thus, the socio-pedagogical necessity of forming a hygienic culture and cultivating the mindset of health care in preparing students for family life consists of the following:

First of all, a healthy lifestyle is important along with the mental development of students in order to develop their academic competence, increase their access to knowledge, and improve their mastery of subjects. Therefore, a healthy lifestyle is very effective in the mental and physical development of students. Therefore, it is possible to form a hygienic culture and prepare for family life by involving students in health activities in higher education.

Secondly, it is possible to explain the necessity of creating a healthy life in the social consciousness by forming a healthy lifestyle culture in students by developing a healthy lifestyle culture in students. That is, by forming the mindset of health care in students, it will be possible to achieve their health and health, as well as to develop knowledge and outlook on the formation of a healthy lifestyle, hygienic culture.

Thirdly, in the context of globalization, in the context of increasing epidemics, it is also important to form the hygienic culture of students within the framework of state policy work aimed at increasing the physical immunity of society, strengthening health, and ensuring people's health.

At the new stage of development of Uzbekistan, the attitude towards family values is also changing. Various ceremonies, family relationships and the procedures for their creation are also being reformed. Social consciousness is changing. Stereotypes that arose during the regime have lost their significance today, and new organizational and theoretical foundations are being formed in the new development conditions. However, the growth of production, the development of technology requires further expansion of requirements for hygienic culture. During the years of independence, the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued decrees and decrees on the organizational foundations of the development of hygienic culture: protecting public health, improving the ecological environment, and organizing the treatment of diseases [5]. Implementation of hygienic culture in all aspects is useful not only for prevention of diseases, but also as a guide for state and non-state organizations in shaping the attitudes of society members in relation to global problems. "Sanitary-epidemiological departments of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan are not only studying the factors that spread the disease, but are implementing organizational principles that create the roots of hygienic culture in people. Today, there are territorial networks of such institutions everywhere, which are aimed at ensuring people's approach to nature and society based on the principles and criteria of hygienic culture. State sanitary control has been established in law-enforcement bodies, in particular, within the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. To date, this department has been dealing with the imposition of fines and cancellation of sales rights to those who violate sanitary-hygienic rules of food quality control. The task now is to ensure that these organizations of the Ministry of Internal Affairs remain an important condition for the development of hygienic culture in people's minds. Therefore, in the process of professional training of law enforcement officers, state programs on hygienic culture, medical guidelines, improvement of the organizational and theoretical foundations of ecological and hygienic education is a condition for the development of hygienic culture. After all, in our country, the work of each organization within the framework of its plan plays an important role in the development of hygienic culture: both organizational and theoretical

foundations. This is clearly expressed in scientific literature, projects, decisions and decrees published in recent years" [6].

Another opportunity for community members to develop a hygienic culture is to involve the general public in keeping the environment clean. This is a priority idea in the domestic policy of the country, and now this opportunity is widely used. In the practical sphere, citizens are developing its introduction in self-management organizations (neighborhoods), public education institutions, and higher educational institutions. Although there are government programs and projects about this, the progress of this work is not high. In general, if we call the indifference of some people in the possibility of attracting the public a subjective reason, we can call the technological "lameness" of some production enterprises an objective factor. This is one side of the matter. The other side of the issue is that both people and organizations have weak control over programmatic performance. It is natural that the need to strengthen control also arises from the organization's capabilities. During the "Red Empire" policy, the false idea that "man is the master of nature" did not give any chance in environmental protection. Currently, Uzbekistan has the opportunity to study practical activities. Hygienic culture should include all these possibilities. Summarizing the opportunities for the development of hygienic culture in the conditions of Uzbekistan, we came to the following conclusions: first, to organize centers that solve hygienic problems in the sectors that have caused health problems in places where the population lives; secondly, to increase the hygienic responsibility of the population - to achieve a new system of opportunities; thirdly, to study the experiences of global environmental protection, to draw appropriate conclusions from it; fourth, extensive involvement of mass media in the formation of hygienic culture; fifth, to use the possibilities of organizing the scientific, practical and theoretical foundations of introducing hygienic culture to all spheres of social life; Sixthly, it is important to make full use of all the opportunities that harmonize ecological and hygienic culture.

References:

1. Akhmedov F.Q, Yaksheeva M.Sh. Pedagogical possibilities of further improvement of physical culture of female students in higher educational institutions // Science and Education" Scientific Journal Volume 1 Issue 1. -B. 408. www.openscience.uz
2. Mattiev I.B. Formation of health care-oriented thinking in students (as an example of business and service sectors). ABSTRACT of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation in Pedagogical Sciences. - Samarkand.: SDChTI. 2019. -B. 5
3. Mattiev I.B. Formation of health care-oriented thinking in students (as an example of business and service sectors). ABSTRACT of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation in Pedagogical Sciences. - Samarkand.: SDChTI. 2019. -B. 5
4. Mattiev I.B. Formation of health care-oriented thinking in students (as an example of business and service sectors). Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation in Pedagogical Sciences AUTHOR ABSTRACT. - Samarkand.: SDChTI. 2019. -B. 5
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the State Program for the Reform of the Health Care System of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 1998 November 10. //Khalk sozi newspaper, issue of November 11, 1998. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the main directions of implementation of the State Program for deepening the reform of

the health care system and its development. 2007 September 19. //Khalk sozi newspaper, issue of September 20, 2007.

6. Asatulloev, I. (2019). The problem of alienation in the philosophy erich fromm. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(1), 123-129.

7. Solikho'jaev S.S., Doschanov B.B. Hygiene. - Tashkent.: Ibn Sina. 1996. (Handbook for students of a higher educational institution); Demidenko N.M. and others. - Hygiene. Tashkent.: 2002. (Handbook for students of a higher educational institution) Holikov P.Kh. and others. Biology. -Tashkent.: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2005., Law on State Sanitary Control. -Tashkent.: 1992.

